

Postoperative Pain Assessment: Emerging Technologies and Clinical Implications

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ARTICLE INFO

REVIEW ARTICLE

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Article history:

Received: 28.04.2026, Accepted: 25.06.2026,

Available/Published Online: 30.06.2026

Acta Medica Ruha, 2026;4(2):87-94.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20845331>

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Postoperative pain is a common clinical problem that significantly affects recovery outcomes and patient safety. Despite the widespread use of conventional pain assessment tools, limitations such as subjectivity and insufficient applicability in certain patient groups necessitate more objective and comprehensive approaches.

Objective: This review aimed to examine current approaches in postoperative pain assessment, evaluate emerging technologies, and highlight their implications for clinical practice and nursing care.

Methods: A narrative literature review was conducted using PubMed and Google Scholar databases. Studies focusing on postoperative pain assessment methods, including both conventional tools and emerging technologies, were reviewed and synthesized.

Results: Conventional pain assessment tools, such as the Visual Analog Scale and Numeric Rating Scale, provide rapid and practical evaluations but are limited by their reliance on patient self-report. Emerging technologies—including mobile health applications, wearable devices, nociception indices, pupillometry, and artificial intelligence-based systems—offer more objective, continuous, and multidimensional assessment opportunities. These technologies enable real-time monitoring, improved accuracy, and enhanced individualized pain management. However, challenges related to validity, cost-effectiveness, data security, and standardization remain significant barriers to widespread clinical implementation.

Conclusion: Emerging technologies have the potential to transform postoperative pain assessment by improving objectivity and supporting personalized care. For effective integration into clinical practice, particularly in nursing care, further high-quality research,

standardization, and professional training are required.

Keywords: Postoperative Pain, Pain, Nursing Care.

INTRODUCTION

Postoperative pain is a typically acute clinical problem that arises following surgical interventions due to disruption of tissue integrity and stimulation of nociceptive nerve endings, directly affecting patients' recovery processes (1, 2). Current data indicate that millions of individuals undergo surgical procedures each year, and a substantial proportion of these patients experience varying levels of pain in the postoperative period (3, 4). Studies in the literature report that approximately 60–75% of postoperative patients experience moderate to severe pain, underscoring the critical importance of effective pain management (5, 6).

Assessment of postoperative pain is one of the most critical nursing activities determining the success of recovery following surgery. Surgical procedures involving extensive tissue damage represent periods of intense nociceptive stimulation and severe pain (7). The high prevalence of postoperative pain and its negative impact on multiple aspects of recovery—physiological, psychological, and functional—necessitate a systematic, objective, and multidimensional approach to pain assessment. Accurate evaluation of postoperative pain is considered a key component of comprehensive postoperative care. Pain is not only a subjective experience but also a stress response that affects hemodynamic stability and physiological well-being. Inadequately controlled pain can lead to complications such as respiratory failure, atelectasis, pulmonary infection, tachycardia, hypertension, delayed wound healing, chronic postoperative pain, and restricted mobilization, thereby prolonging hospital stay and increasing healthcare costs. Therefore, regular, structured, and evidence-based pain assessment practices in the postoperative period facilitate individualized analgesic treatment and contribute to early detection of complications, ultimately enhancing patient safety (8–10).

A review of postoperative pain assessment methods reveals the long-standing use of both unidimensional and multidimensional tools.

These methods have been employed in clinical practice to accurately and reliably measure patients' pain experiences. Unidimensional tools allow rapid and practical assessment of pain intensity. The most commonly used include the Visual Analog Scale, Numeric Rating Scale, and Verbal Descriptor Scale, where patients express their pain using numerical values or verbal descriptors. These tools provide a practical and reliable approach, particularly in settings requiring rapid assessment, such as intensive care units and postoperative recovery areas (11). In contrast, multidimensional pain assessment tools evaluate not only pain intensity but also its quality, duration, and the patient's emotional and functional responses. These tools enable a more comprehensive evaluation by revealing the impact of pain on quality of life, mobility, sleep patterns, and psychological status. Multidimensional scales support the personalization of analgesic treatment plans and enhance the effectiveness of multidisciplinary care processes. When used together, these approaches allow not only rapid measurement of postoperative pain but also a holistic understanding of the patient's experience, enabling optimization of treatment plans. Consequently, both patient safety and quality of care are significantly improved (2, 12).

In addition to these assessment tools, next-generation pain measurement technologies integrated with current advancements enable more precise and continuous patient monitoring (13). These tools, supported by physiological parameters and technological infrastructure, provide a comprehensive evaluation and allow more objective and reliable monitoring of postoperative pain. They may significantly contribute to the development of individualized pain management strategies and improvement of postoperative care quality (4). Although studies on next-generation pain assessment tools exist in the literature, they typically focus on a single technology (14–16). For nurses responsible for assessing postoperative pain and guiding patients to the next stage of pain management, staying updated with current assessment tools is essential for delivering high-quality patient care.

In this review, studies on next-generation pain measurement tools were comprehensively examined and presented to colleagues. The literature search was conducted using the

PubMed database and Google Scholar. The aim of this review is to comprehensively evaluate current approaches to postoperative pain assessment, their impact on clinical outcomes, and their role in nursing care, thereby contributing to the development of evidence-based practices.

CONVENTIONAL PAIN MEASUREMENT TOOLS AND THEIR LIMITATIONS

Accurate assessment of postoperative pain requires careful identification of how pain is perceived by the individual and the associated physiological, psychological, and behavioral responses (17). In this context, obtaining a detailed patient history, conducting continuous clinical observation, and using validated standard pain assessment scales are of critical importance (19).

Traditional pain assessment relies on patient self-report tools such as the Numeric Rating Scale and the Visual Analog Scale. However, these tools may introduce recall bias, particularly in chronic pain conditions, and may be inadequate for patients with cognitive impairment or communication difficulties (8, 19). Selecting an appropriate scale, reliably measuring pain intensity, and consistently using the same scale throughout treatment are clinically essential. Nevertheless, pain assessment is inherently challenging. This difficulty is closely related to factors such as age, developmental level, prior pain experiences, and environmental influences. Additionally, in some patients, subjective expression of pain may not be possible due to age, cognitive limitations, communication barriers, existing pathologies, sedation, or other clinical conditions. In such cases, information obtained from caregivers and healthcare professionals, along with specially developed assessment scales, may be utilized. Pain measurement methods can generally be categorized into four main groups: subjective self-report measures, behavioral indicators, physiological parameters, and combined approaches. An ideal pain assessment tool is expected to be reliable across various clinical settings, sensitive, unbiased, internally consistent, and easy to understand. However, none of the existing scales fully meet all these criteria simultaneously. Only a limited number demonstrate strong validity and reliability, and

their suitability may vary depending on the clinical context in which they are applied (20).

NEXT-GENERATION PAIN ASSESSMENT TOOLS

Mobile Technologies

Mobile technologies encompass portable, computer-based devices such as smartphones, tablets, handheld gaming consoles, and media players (21). In recent years, these technologies have been widely used in clinical practice to facilitate postoperative home monitoring, standardize pain assessment, and contribute to the personalization of treatment processes. Specialized mobile applications developed to perform biopsychosocial pain assessment in patients undergoing orthopedic surgery have gained attention in the literature. One such system is a digital monitoring application integrated with a short message service and operating on a database connected to a local IP address using Twilio infrastructure (Figure 1). In patients undergoing total hip and knee arthroplasty and spinal surgery, daily pain levels (rated 0–10) and opioid use were monitored through the system from the postoperative period up to the sixth week. Additionally, potential opioid-related side effects were recorded within the application. The system continued sending notifications if uninterrupted opioid use persisted for four days. Patients not using opioids were directed to final evaluation questions. Patients who did not respond for three consecutive days were followed up via direct contact by healthcare professionals. This mobile system has been reported to facilitate patient monitoring, improve data integrity, and positively contribute to patient satisfaction (14).

Figure 1. Twilio

Wearable Electronic Devices

Wearable technologies are defined as systems that can be integrated into the body, enable users to access information anytime and anywhere, allow bidirectional interaction, and possess independent energy sources and processing capabilities. Common examples include smart glasses, smartwatches, smart belts, smart textiles, smart shoes, and fitness tracking bands (14). Increasingly adopted in healthcare, these devices offer significant potential for obtaining objective and continuous data, particularly for pain monitoring. The use of wearable electronic devices enables more objective, reproducible, and standardized assessment of pain levels. The literature emphasizes the importance of integrating these devices with gold-standard clinical scales for pain measurement. Accordingly, a holistic pain assessment model is established by combining physiological parameters with validated tools such as the Numeric Rating Scale, Visual Analog Scale, and Brief Pain Inventory (22). Incorporating physiological parameters into the assessment process provides a particular advantage in elderly individuals who have difficulty expressing pain or have limited cognitive capacity (23). In this respect, wearable technologies enable the simultaneous collection of subjective and objective data, positioning them as a powerful complement to modern pain management (8).

Electromyographic Belt and Smartwatches

The electromyographic belt (Figure 2), developed by Sherman et al., is an innovative tool that records muscle tension, trunk movement, and pain in musculoskeletal conditions. Worn on the lower back, it uses three electrodes to measure right and left paraspinal muscle tension and overall movement. It also includes prompts for patients to rate pain and fatigue. Visual Analog Scale applications have shown a relationship between increased muscle tension and fluctuations in intermittent low back and muscle pain. However, limited information on its operational principles and usage restricts wider clinical adoption (24).

In the smartwatch system developed by Mardini et al., daily mobility and pain severity in older adults with knee osteoarthritis were monitored using GPS data (25). Pain is assessed three

times daily using the Numeric Rating Scale or a verbal scale, while real-time sensor feedback enables continuous evaluation during movement (23). With sensors for activity and location tracking, smartwatches support continuous, long-term data collection and remote monitoring, facilitating communication with healthcare professionals. These features make them valuable complementary tools for pain assessment and treatment monitoring (24).

Figure 2. Electromyographic Belt Monitoring

Nociception Level Index Monitoring

The Nociception Level Index (Figure 3) is an innovative measurement tool that simultaneously analyzes multiple parameters using artificial intelligence. This index is based on a patented algorithmic technology that evaluates individuals' physiological responses to pain in real time, continuously, and noninvasively. In clinical practice, there is a need for standardized methods that enable healthcare professionals to assess patient-specific pain responses in an objective, reproducible, and reliable manner within a holistic pain management framework. With its multidimensional measurement approach, the nociception level index emerges as a promising tool in pain assessment processes. Updated every five seconds, the index provides a dimensionless score ranging from 0 to 100, where lower values indicate reduced sympathetic activity (16). Therefore, the nociception level index is considered a significant technology with the potential to contribute to future research on pain monitoring and to support clinical decision-making processes.

Figure 3. Nociception Level Index Monitoring

Analgesia Nociception Index Monitor

The Analgesia Nociception Index (ANI) monitor (Figure 4) is an assessment tool based on autonomic nervous system responses, primarily operating through the analysis of respiratory-related cardiac rhythm variability (15). A recent systematic review examining studies involving orthopedic surgical patients reported that monitoring with this device contributes to more accurate prediction throughout the surgical process (26). These findings indicate that the ANI monitor may serve as a valuable tool to support clinical decision-making in pain assessment.

Figure 4. Analgesia Nociception Index Monitor

Pupillometry

Pupillometry objectively assesses nociception via sympathetic responses of the central nervous system to painful stimuli (Figure 5). It is particularly useful in pediatric, critically ill, and communication-impaired patients. Portable automated pupillometers accurately measure

light and dilation reflexes. The method is used to determine nociception, monitor analgesic response, and evaluate regional anesthesia effectiveness. Pupillary oscillations also reflect central opioid effects. The pupil pain index, based on reflex dilation to electrical stimuli, correlates with postoperative pain, supporting its use in pain assessment and opioid management (12).

In a study of 100 general surgery patients, pupillary reflex dilation measured before and after morphine showed a significant association with reported pain, with dilation decreasing after morphine. Similarly, reflex dilation amplitude in response to incision pressure correlated positively with pain scores, suggesting value in non-communicative patients. However, tetanic stimulation may cause discomfort in awake individuals, limiting use to anesthesia or sedation. In persistent pain conditions such as trauma or cancer, the clinical value of absolute pupillary dilation remains unclear (27).

Figure 5. PLR-3000 Pupillometer

Artificial Intelligence

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into healthcare has significantly accelerated transformative technological advances in pain assessment and management. Traditional statistical methods are often insufficient given the complexity of pain-related biomarkers and the substantial interindividual variability. In contrast, AI-based approaches enable comprehensive analysis of multidimensional physiological and behavioral data—such as heart rate, electromyography signals, and facial expressions—allowing pain to be assessed more

objectively, continuously, and with greater accuracy (28). These methods offer clear advantages over conventional strategies based on patient self-report and clinician observation. Recent studies have demonstrated that machine learning algorithms can predict chronic pain levels with high accuracy, thereby reducing reliance on subjective pain scales (29). Furthermore, the integration of AI into clinical decision support systems enhances the reliability, consistency, and scientific robustness of treatment recommendations derived from large-scale data analyses (18). Collectively, these technological advancements not only improve the effectiveness of pain management and the efficiency of clinical processes but also enhance patients' treatment experiences and quality of life, supporting the emergence of personalized, technology-driven next-generation pain management paradigms.

Limitations of Next-Generation Measurement Tools

Wearable sensors, biomarker-based measurement devices, and AI-supported analytical systems generate more reliable pain-related data by continuously monitoring physiological parameters such as heart rate, muscle activity, electrodermal activity, and other indicators in real time (29). When integrated with machine learning algorithms, these systems analyze the collected data to create individualized pain profiles and support the development of personalized treatment plans (31, 32). This enables dynamic adaptation of treatment processes, optimization of pain management, and reduced reliance on pharmacological interventions. However, these technologies have several limitations. Sensor inaccuracies, device-related technical issues, and user-related errors may compromise data accuracy (29). Moreover, the pain experience cannot be fully explained by physiological parameters alone; psychological state, emotional responses, and environmental factors may not always be reflected in measurements. The complex and often non-transparent nature of AI algorithms can hinder interpretation of model outputs and increase the risk of erroneous predictions (31). Continuous data collection and transmission also raise concerns regarding the security and privacy of personal health information (5). Additionally, nurses' ethical responsibilities in pain management—relieving pain, advocating for patient rights, and ensuring

informed care—must be upheld (32). While digital tools may reduce workload, preserving human-centered care remains essential. Finally, the high cost of these systems and the lack of standardization in measurement methods represent significant barriers to their widespread clinical adoption (6).

CONCLUSION

Next-generation measurement tools in postoperative pain assessment offer substantial potential to transform clinical practice by enabling more objective, continuous, and multidimensional evaluation of pain. Innovative approaches—including wearable technologies, AI-based systems, physiological indices, and digital monitoring tools—not only address the limitations of traditional methods relying solely on patient self-report but also facilitate the development of individualized pain management strategies. These technologies allow earlier and more precise detection of pain, more effective monitoring of responses to analgesic therapy, and improved patient safety. However, challenges remain in integrating these tools into clinical practice, including issues related to measurement accuracy, validity across diverse patient populations, cost-effectiveness, data security, and ethical considerations. Moreover, the inherently multidimensional nature of pain, which cannot be fully captured by physiological parameters alone, underscores the necessity of holistic assessment approaches.

From a nursing perspective, the effective and informed use of these technologies by nurses—who play a central role in postoperative pain management—is critical. Nurses must adopt a holistic approach that goes beyond monitoring technological data to also consider patients' subjective experiences, psychosocial conditions, and individual needs. In this context, integrating next-generation measurement tools into nursing practice can support clinical decision-making, enhance care quality, facilitate early intervention, and improve patient outcomes. However, effective implementation requires strengthening nurses' education, standardizing clinical protocols, and promoting multidisciplinary collaboration.

In conclusion, although next-generation measurement tools offer significant advantages in postoperative pain assessment, further high-

quality, comparative studies are needed to determine in which patient populations and clinical settings these technologies are most effective. Future research should more comprehensively establish their clinical validity, reliability, and cost-effectiveness, thereby contributing to the advancement of nursing care and the broader adoption of evidence-based pain management practices.

DESCRIPTIONS

No financial support.

No conflict of interest.

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